

PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A "GREEN ECONOMY" IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article mentions that in order to improve the socio-economic lifestyle of the population in the Republic of Uzbekistan, attention is paid not only to strategic issues but also to global processes and problems.*

The need to accelerate the transition to the "green" economy and conduct a policy aimed at development based on the principles of the green economy was explained not only to help eliminate environmental problems but also to improve the social and economic lifestyle of our people.

Scientific and practical recommendations are given as a result of the experience of statistic information and research.

Keywords: *environmental problems, alternative energy, economic growth, green economy, green development, ecology.*

In order to ensure long-term economic growth and stability in Uzbekistan, deep processing of the economy and export goods products and a rapid increase in the share of finished products with high added value are being improved.

President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev said at a video electricity meeting on March 31, 2022, that "international experts are forecasting that the current complex situation in the world economy will last a long time." This will not adversely affect the price of the domestic market, especially food prices and inflation," and put before the heads of the economic complex a number of tasks on reducing the negative impact of the situation in the world economy, supporting entrepreneurs, curbing inflation, ensuring price stability in the consumer market, investments, exports, and other areas.

For the sustainable development of the economy, its lack of mutual proportionality in the cross-section of networks and sectors negatively affects the inefficient use of economic resources in the country, as a result of which economic crises increase, unemployment rises, and inflation rises above the established natural level, all of which negatively affect the socio-economic way of life of the population.

It is known that in achieving sustainable economic growth, in the process of modernization in the economy and the implementation of structural changes, the use of economic policies based on foreign experience and the involvement of foreign investment in economic sectors are of particular importance. Today, as a solution to environmental problems, which have become a global issue not only in our country but throughout the world, the policy of "green" development is widely introduced in order to stabilize our economy.

Despite the fact that in scientific research the concept of "green economy" was first used in 1989, its essence has been interpreted in different ways so far. In some sources, the "green economy" is studied as new sectors of the economy that promote the improvement of the nature of the country; in some studies, the "green economy" is studied as new technologies and

ecosystems that help and benefit nature; and in the third group of studies, the "green economy" is the transition to a new stage of development aimed at creating environmentally friendly products.

A common, relatively complete definition of the concept of "green economy" was developed by the UN Environmental Protection Program (UNEP), which states that "green economy" is an economy that leads to improved welfare and social equality of people, significant reduction of environmental risks, and ecological deficit". As a result of the above definitions, we can say that there is no universally accepted concept of this concept, which continues to be formed. The concept can be applied to economic networks, green economic theory and principles, and green economic policy.

The main objective of the green economy concept is to ensure sustainable economic growth and improve the quality of Environmental Protection and social integration while increasing investment. From this point of view, in order to develop economic networks and ensure their sustainability, public, private, and foreign investments should be directed at the environmental and social factors of sustainable development on a large scale. The goal of the "green economy" is to achieve sustainable economic growth by making good use of natural and limited resources and relatively reducing factors that negatively affect nature.

It is believed that this economic system is not sufficiently evolutionary, despite the fact that it is achieving positive results in improving the social status of the population. Degradation of ecology (climate change, desertification, bio-diversity), depletion of natural capital, increasing poverty scale, lack of food, fresh water, electricity, and economic and environmental inequality between countries cause the current system to be imperfect. Somehow, on the territory of Uzbekistan, the transition to this system, which is not a green economy system but a "brown economy," is applied.

Degradation of ecology, desertification in one area of the earth as a result of climate change, aggravating the financial and social situation of the population, an increase in water level in another area, endangering the layer of the population living on the coast, flooding. In recent years, the development of modernization in the economy has led to an increase in fuel-intensive technologies, exacerbating the fuel crisis. According to the forecasts of the International Energy Agency, as a result of increased production and limited resources, the cost of oil in the economic and financial markets in 2030 is planned to be 200 dollars.

The consequences of global crises lead to a rise in the same unemployment rate in developing and developed countries, an increase in poverty, and an aggravation of the social situation.

The use of energy-efficient, latest types of technologies in industries and buildings and the development of the transport system have an important place in the formation of a "green economy". This not only releases low emissions into the environment by reducing energy (oil, gas, electricity, etc.). In light of the negative impact on ecology, it is important to develop the production of electric cars in order to change this situation in a positive way. Electric cars are considered a transport ratio after industrial waste.

Another way to preserve modern ecology is to establish the rational use of natural resources and introduce the necessary technologies for the development of this direction. Renewable energy is a source of energy derived from the environmental energy flow. These include solar, wind, water resources, geothermal sources, industrial and municipal biogas, and biogas derived from

agricultural waste. Alternative energy sources play a large role in saving primary hydrocarbon resources in cities and ensuring the country's energy security.

Therefore, in the strategy of the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the "green economy" in 2019–2030, the following are established: In terms of energy efficiency in the following base sectors of the economy:

in the field of electro-energy: reconstruction and modernization of existing power plants by installing steam-gas and gas-pipe devices, complete automation of processes, and digitization of controls;

in the field of thermal energy: introduction of new technologies in the production of thermal energy; reconstruction of outdated technological equipment in boilers; modernization with new computing equipment; in the oil and gas field: reduction of losses in the processes of natural gas extraction, transportation, and redistribution in exchange for modernization of compressor stations; low and medium-pressure gas distribution systems;

On the diversification of energy resource consumption and the development of the use of renewable energy sources:

in the field of renewable energy sources:

liberalization of tariff policies related to the production, transportation, and purchase of energy from renewable energy sources; support of enterprises producing equipment using such sources;

in the field of construction and operation of buildings: implementation of state programs to improve the energy efficiency of buildings, revision of building standards at least once every 5 years, implementation of closed systems of heat supply through the system of tightening energy efficiency standards, application of a system of incentives for energy conservation, introduction of tariffs;

in the transport sector: expansion of the production of vehicles, electric cars, and cars with hybrid engines with improved descriptions in the directions of energy efficiency and ecological cleanliness within the framework of the Euro-4 standards; gradual abandonment of hydrocarbon fuels; promotion of the development of electric transport systems; creation of new transport and logistics systems; improvement of road infrastructure;

To mitigate and adapt to the consequences of climate change, to improve the efficiency of natural resource use, and to preserve natural ecosystems:

in the field of aquaculture: prevention of further salinity and deterioration of the quality of the earth; construction and reconstruction of hydraulic structures, pumping stations, and reservoirs; extensive application of information and communication technologies and innovations in aquaculture; application of energy-efficient and water-saving technologies in irrigation of agricultural crops;

in the field of agriculture: restoration of degraded pastures, diversification of agricultural crops, barbing pollution of water sources with agricultural waste, creation of non-destructive processes, risk-resistant and suitable varieties and breeds of plants and animals, such as salinity, drought, and climatic whims;

in the field of solid waste: full coverage of the entire population in the solid waste collection and decontamination service; the introduction of modern and effective systems for the collection and processing of solid waste; the use of solid waste as alternative energy sources.

Analyzing the development of the sectors of the country's economy on the principles of the green economy, we see that the situation is not a joy either. One of the first prominent problems in the analysis and research of the extent to which the green economy is present in sectors of the economy in the sources is that it can be explained that there is little research due to the low level of transparency in the data as well as the near absence of information in this direction. At the same time, it is necessary to note that since the green economy has risen to the level of public policy, it is necessary to widely introduce the practice of keeping information related to the greening processes of the economy in financial, economic, and other reports and statistics. Below, we try to analyze the state of the green economy in some sectors of the economy based on the available data.

Table 1

Production of electricity from alternative energy sources, million kW.H

Production of electricity from alternative energy sources	2018-year	2019-year	2020-year	2021-year	2022-year
Electricity generated by solar power plants	0,2	0,1	0,03	49,0	445,7
Electricity generated by wind farms	-	15,5	-	1,2	-

According to the data presented in the table, the indicators of electricity produced by wind farms in our republic in 2019 and 2021 are 15.5 and 1.2 million kW, respectively. The generation of electricity by wind farms was not reported in 2018, 2020, or 2022.

Due to the fact that our country is considered a sunny, sky-clear country instead of being located on Earth, the use of solar elective stations is at the forefront of alternative energy production. Energy production by the solar power plant began to rise in 2021 (49.0 million kWh). This is due to the fact that on August 27, 2021, the first solar power plant was launched in Uzbekistan in the Navaiy region. Its capacity is 100 MW. The construction of this facility is considered the first big step we have taken toward a green economy and will cost \$80 million a year. In addition to saving natural gas consumption, the cubic meter was also the basis for a 160,000-ton reduction in greenhouse gases emitted into the atmosphere.

In 2022, the rate will reach 445.7 million kWh. A solar power plant was also put into operation in Nurabad District of the Samarkand region of our country. It is a 100 MW solar photovoltaic plant built by Total Eren of France, generating 260 Mt/H of electricity per year and providing electricity to more than 80,000 households. In addition, the launch of the station will save 78 million cubic meters of natural gas per year and prevent the release of 100 thousand tons of harmful emissions into the atmosphere. This amount of saved gas will provide natural gas to all households in our country within 10 days.

However, during 2018–2020, the electricity generated by solar power plants in our republic was 0.2 million kWh, 0.1 million kWh, and 0.03 million kWh. Despite the fact that the transition to a "green economy" is also cited in the "action strategy" for 2017 and 2021, the lack of complete fulfillment of tasks by mutated leaders, as well as the increased attention to other sectors of the economy due to the pandemic, caused this figure to fall to its lowest level in 2020.

Despite the fact that in our republic there is a territorial opportunity to use alternative and renewable electricity, this type of electricity is not used to the fullest extent of its reserves. According to experts, an average of 300 days is considered solar, as a result of which 50 trillion

are equal to 973 million tons of conditional fuel. This is more than the total fuel reserves that we have identified in our country. In addition, the natural conditions of our country make it convenient to use solar and wind energy.

In addition, by increasing the construction of "solar houses", its desire, supply of hot water, and photoelectric energy contribute to a sharp decrease in environmental problems. In order to increase the volume of sources of clean energy in our country, increasing investments in the green economy and wide involvement of domestic and foreign investments will serve to ensure the prospects of this area. Based on the above points, we give the following suggestions for the purpose of moving to and developing a "green economy":

- rational and efficient use of available resources;
- making decisions of the government and territorial authorities on the widespread use of "green" energy;
- given the skill about the economical use of electricity in the consumption of the population layer, development of practical proposals and developments for the construction of a "green" house and premises.

In conclusion, in order to achieve a sustainable long-term economy, it is necessary to provide society with modernization and innovative technologies. In turn, the use of alternative and natural energies is of particular importance in these actions. Because achieving a sustainable economy requires that the generation living now and in the future have enough facilities, Therefore, the "green economy" is also the most optimal economic policy in the world community.

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